

STE(A)M ATLAS

Three Roadmaps. One STE(A)M destination.

The **STE(A)M ATLAS** brings together three EC funded roadmaps to STE(A)M Education. The roadmaps champion complementary approaches to support a holistic approach to teaching and learning where **STEM, Arts, and non-STEM topics are fully integrated for an immersive and meaningful learning experience.**

Each project interprets the “A” differently—from “Arts” to “All”—reflecting a shared ambition to foster transdisciplinarity. Together, **SENSE, SEER and Road-STEAMer** tackle current challenges through coordinated action at policy, curricula, and classroom levels.

SENSE. drives transformative change for future-making education, mobilising aesthetic inquiry and spatial literacy for equity, well-being and social and educational inclusion. Its STE(A)M Academy brings together theory, evidence and practice to support action at local and global levels.

The SEER sets clear pathways for all stakeholders to standardise STE(A)M in European curricula and schools and offers an Impact Assessment Mechanism for projects and the workplan for a STE(A)M competences certification framework for educators.

Road-STEAMer promotes the integration of STE(A)M education into funding and regulatory frameworks, focusing on strengthening curricula, enhancing teacher training, and fostering inclusive learning environments.

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Recommendations for a STE(A)M future

EUROPEAN COMMISSION

- Encourage and fund the development of innovative learning environments—such as community centres, online platforms, and maker spaces—that can be adapted to suit a variety of learning styles and needs, promoting the establishment of positive emotional experiences that can enable learners to thrive.
- Fund research and exchange projects aimed at developing a variety of STE(A)M educational resources in multiple languages, grounded in culturally responsive pedagogies and differentiated teaching strategies. This should ideally involve the collaboration of civil society and grassroots organisations.
- Create an EU STE(A)M mission for coordinated action towards systemic change of the educational landscape across the EU, promoting the adoption of innovative, responsive and inclusive educational practices addressing multiple drivers of exclusion

MEMBER STATES

- Incorporate STE(A)M methodologies into initial teacher education and professional development, to reflect a combination of content knowledge and pedagogical practices, in line with changes in the curriculum and assessment frameworks. Training opportunities should incorporate structured mentoring, peer collaboration, and recognition (certification or credits) to foster sustainable teacher growth.
- Establish clear legislative frameworks to education-industry collaboration while preventing undue corporate influence
- Promote open schooling approaches and community-based STE(A)M activities linked to real-world challenges (e.g. climate change) to empower learners as agents of change

EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

- Understand and empower learners: Recognize learner expectations, enhance knowledge ownership, and create spaces for speculation and imagination throughout the learning process
- Actively encourage collaboration and partnerships with external stakeholders (industry, research, community, etc.) and promote the creation of living labs in line with open schooling approaches
- Actively encourage collaboration across subjects and grade levels, protecting time for teacher collaboration and professional development, and creating incentives for innovation and mentoring